
Craft skills exposure in a work team's routinized creative practice.

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Abstract: This paper explores collectively shared and sustained craftsmanship, worker agency instantiated by physical fixtures and collective creativity in work processes and contrasts this practice with a pilot test of extended digitisation of tools, i.e. the application of augmented reality. The ability of the collective to establish, maintain and recover meaningful activities, procedures and processes is important in most workplaces and in collaboration in social groups. Collective know-how, i.e. procedural memory. The unit of study is an industrial team creative practice developing fixtures to support the assembly procedures of lever tumbler locks. Collective practices establish the skills needed to carry out a particular set of procedures. In summary, craft skills exist relationally - in the relationships between materials, objects, technologies, memory, feeling, different human actors and the chains of associations between them.

Keywords: workplace agency; fixture methodology; craftsmanship; collective creativity; relational skill development.

1 Introduction

This paper explores collectively shared and sustained craftsmanship, workers agency instantiated by physical fixtures and collective creativity in work processes as well as under extended digitization of tools, i.e., augmented reality environment.

The two case studies that form the basis of this paper have been carried out in one of the companies in a business consortium in industrial design consisting of six small companies with a total of 40 employees. The site where this study collects qualitative data is an entrepreneurial contract manufacturing lock product company, operating in four business areas: marine, institutions, industry, residential homes. The overall business strategy is to extend lock products life cycle. This site is located in the region of mid-east Sweden with 150-year lock production tradition, fostering competitive skills on an international market, producing components and assembly lever tumbler locks. The business model, based on the employees craftsmanship, is concisely formulated "low

volume and high mix”, have established a corporate culture of pride and integrity in relation to the region's multinational companies within the same industry.

The quality in lock production processes and component assembling procedures have been developed within the work collective practice over a long time. In these routinized practices a shared understanding of what it means to manufacture, assemble and quality check different types of mechanical lever tumbler locks resides.

As a consequence of the company's digitalisation strategy, a digital production system is implemented. This in turn leads to further decisions to extend the company's processes and tools with various types of digital and automation technologies. The intention to use AR technology as a replacement for e.g., managerial instructions or the interaction between trainees imitating, mentors demonstrating and commenting. Traditionally, these strategies are used in situations where the instruction of work processes or the transfer of skills requires extensive product understanding and craftsmanship.

Two case studies generated one set of qualitative empirical data each, that are contrasted and analysed comparatively. The first, and main, case concerns routinised assembly procedures using fixtures of various types of material, which has evolved tacitly to a well-established but overlooked emergent methodology. The second case is a pilot project testing the use of augmented reality technology to capture lock assembly procedures with the aim of training new employees and support employee rotation between different workstation products and business areas.

Several aspects and questions arise in this mix of routinized body-hand-skills-material-patterns. The overarching problem concerns craft skills, how it is created and materialized collectively on the one hand, and the impact of digitalized tools, augmented reality and artificial intelligence on craft skills, training, and the organizing of work on the other:

What is augmented, diminished, or disrupted?

2 Theory

The ability of the collective to establish, maintain and recover meaningful activities, procedures and processes is important in most workplaces and other types of collaboration in social groups (Katzenbach & Smith, 1993). Donahue (2024) refers to this capacity of groups to store and retrieve doings as collective procedural memory, the memory collectively possessed of how to do things (Ibid, p.13). This know-how can be contrasted to declarative knowledge mainly because procedures that are difficult/complicated to express in words (Ullman, 2004, in Donahue, 2024). In collective practices, skills necessary to perform a certain set of procedures are established (emerge?). In this study, the practice of what it means to produce tumblers corresponds to liver locks, but to achieve this, a number of procedures need to be performed, such as assembling all the components into a flawlessly functioning lock. That the collective is able to produce reliably is an expression of collective procedural memory, (i.e., ability conception according to) Donahue (2024). Reckwitz (2002) clarify that this shared knowledge is a collective way of understanding. *“Just as the bodily activities are ‘social’ as a consequence of their stable reproduction beyond the limits of space, time and single individuals, their ‘corresponding’ forms of understanding must be ‘collective’ ...”* (ibid., p.253).

Collective creativity: agency, problem solving and tinkering.

Collectivist perspectives on creativity emphasizes the role of social interaction and communication in creative action. That is, social collaboration and exchange drives creativity, not only in the sense that we collaborate with others while creating something, but also when we build on each other's ideas and perspectives as part of our own creative processes. Hargadon & Bechky (2006) investigated collective creativity by focusing on the confluence of old ideas and observed how the "creative" value of those ideas evolved through their combination i.e., confluence, with others' ideas. That is, collective practice of creativity is the result of co-creation, arising from exchanges between people and the socially based combinations of differences, rather than the activity of isolated minds. Therefore, the study of creativity requires in-depth analysis of the visible and invisible networks of collaboration that promote creative ideas, products, and practices (Corazza & Glăveanu (2020). Team based creativity is thus the ability to switch between generating divergent contributions (ideas) and to establish stabilizing points of convergence is a collectively maintained competence (Backström & Söderberg, 2016; Köping Olsson 2021).

Goller and Bessant (2024) summarizes that creative problem solving is about exploring the problem through social interaction and exchange as well as tinkering with the elements of the given situation. They repeat Isaksen and Treffingers (1985) definition of creative problem solving:

" Creativity is the making and communicating of meaningful new connections, to help us think of many possibilities; to help us think and experience in varied ways and using different points of view; to help us think of new and unusual possibilities; and to guide us in generating and selecting alternatives. These new connections and possibilities must result in something of value for the individual, group, organization, or society" (in Isaksen & Tidd, 2006).

Relational affordances: routinizing, mediating, and enabling objects (fixtures)

Bonetti (2022) investigated how AI-technology were implemented in an integrative practice of retailing, comprised of many dispersed practices. They found that for the AI usage to be sustained a practice of co-evolution must be recursive and enabled via intentional knowledge transfers. They argue that a collaborative process needs to be orchestrated in which this practice is co-envisioned, co-adapted, and co-(re)aligned.

According to Davis & Chouinard (2016), affordance theory shows how technologies fit the user's activities. Based on the conditions that the use of a 3D-printed fixture or an AR application establishes in terms of affordance, it is emphasized in which ways technologies can have affordance, for whom and under what circumstances. According to Davis & Chouinard (2016), this can indicate the different ways in which a technology can presuppose, require, encourage, discourage, refuse, and allow social action, depending on the users' perception, skill, and cultural and institutional legitimacy in relation to the technological object.

Digital instructions in augmented reality

Hooijdonk et al. (2022) have studied how objects in virtual reality technology (VR) affect cognitive flexibility and found that this type of environment risks increasing mental fixation. The expectations of increased flexibility of the studied company's workers through the support of AR-based work instructions are important aspects to consider when evaluating the work organization. The question is how these virtual environments affect the creative process. Introducing a virtual environment which includes new forms

of social interactions and the digital affordances of virtual objects. The impact of these artificial elements on the creative process is starting to be studied e.g., Guegan, Nelson, & Lubart, (2017).

Kofler and Walder (2024) studied the effects of digitalization in the craft sector. They have found that even though companies are open to technological change and ready to invest in it, the lack of competencies or employees rejecting digital transformation. They argue that digitalization and the value of practice-based skills, therefore, need to be integrated into the narrative of everyday creativity practice. Kofler and Walder suggest with reference to Sennett (2008) that because doing and making is central to craftspeople this integration strategy can be the potentiality of the skilled embodiment of the practical.

3 Methodology

Using an ethnographic research approach with recurring field studies at a craft-oriented contract manufacturing company in the lock industry, data collection has been conducted via field notes and video recorded observations of manual lock assembly, as well as recorded and transcribed interviews with several workers in the assembly department and the site manager and the CEO in the management.

With this research approach, the observations were primarily participatory, i.e., the researcher did not just observe factors in situations and behaviours, but rather became involved in the events and took part in the activities. For example, when studying a worker assembling a lock, the researcher discusses with the assembler and also tries to carry out of the steps himself. This degree of involvement aims to understand more deeply, to grasp and feel the material, the surface of the components, the weight of the tools, etc., and to gain an emotional understanding of how hard a screw needs to be tightened, or how it should feel and sound when the keys of a lock work or not. The underlying purpose of this approach is to form understandings of what is actually going on rather than reading or listening to general descriptions of the assembly procedure, for example in a drawing or checklist accounts.

This also has implications for data collection. As the researcher has not defined in advance what will happen in the observed situations, different types of data are collected at the same time. In this study, short field notes were taken as the opportunity arose, while photographs were taken of specific events and objects, and parallel sequences of work procedures were captured on video. Methods of data collection were therefore: a) observations, field notes, photos, videos, b) semi-structured interviews some in dialogue format with two interviewees, c) ethnographic interviews, asking questions in the moment. All recorded material has been transcribed (in Swedish) and then translated to English utilizing the DeepL.com software.

Research design.

In line with Orlikowski (2000) we observe and make sense of actor's interaction with the technology at hand. A work team's joint iterative testing of fixtures to facilitate the assembly of mechanical locks is described and analysed in terms of creative agency. This fixture-based approach is contrasted with nascent adoption of AI/AR application. The research design of this study can be compared to Bonettis et al., (2022), who also pitted orchestrated collaborative processes against collective creative agency in the development and use of fixtures and AR-based instructions respectively. This study thus consists of two cases, 1) Fixture methodology and relational ontology and

2) the AI/AR application development and pilot testing.

Data collection, case 1) Fixture methodology in a relational ontology

The lock assembly team is spread over six workstations and a method developer works in an adjacent prototyping lab. The fieldwork for this case was carried out as participant observation on three occasions of about three hours each, one week apart, focusing on the marine lock products business area and the prototype lab where the fixtures are designed. During these observations, photographs and short video sequences are taken, as well as field notes. Embedded in the observations are ethnographic in-situ interviews to capture the reflective practice of the assemblers.

The fourth field visit consisted of a dialogue interview with a marine lock assembler and the method developer. This was conducted off-site in the company's conference room on September 13, 2023. All events and interviews were documented with audio recordings, which were transcribed and translated into English.

Data collection, case 2) AI/AR application development and pilot testing

This delimited case study focuses on the development and pilot testing of an application using augmented reality technology that aims to enable potential workers to acquire process understanding and train their ability to assemble all the components into a working lock.

The main observation concerned the pilot testing which was carried out for 1.5 hours in the company's premises, a traditionally furnished conference room for ten people. Directly following the pilot test, an evaluation dialogue was held for about 30 minutes, involving all the people present during the testing of the AR application. The empirical data presented in this paper are excerpts from the fully transcribed dialogues during the pilot testing session, as well as the evaluative dialogue.

Data analysis

Analysis of qualitative empirical data involves both “headwork” and “textwork”, i.e., analysis starts during data collection, under observation of actions, sensing the situation, writing of initial field notes, reflecting on experiences. The analysis work has iterated observations and field notes, actors' behaviors, respondents' accounts, and results from previous research. The study's theoretical contribution has emerged from the theory of practice as an exploration of embedded mental activities for understanding and knowledge in a complex of actions. Which means that the analysis connects bodily routines for behavior, mental routines for developing and deepening understandings in the use of objects (Reckwitz, 2002).

Participants in the session for pilot test of AR-application

Total of eight persons in a conference room at the case company, distributed as follows: Three participants from the tech/innovation partner: the leader of the research project work package, the programmer, and a doctoral student.

Four participants from the company: the apprentice (a worker from the production section), the company expert, the site manager, and the CEO.

One participant from the university, the observing ethnographer.

4 Empirical data and findings

Case 1: Fixture methodology and relational ontology.

The process of fixtures development starts with paper and pencil, sketching main features/functions and then build a physical prototype. Very rough and preliminary since the purpose is first to have something to show and discuss with the assemblers (staff, operators). In parallel there is a lot of tinkering with the specific new lock components to find out the mechanical functions, testing alternative ways of screwing them together and let several in the staff or specific customer check if it works as expected. Most often, changes and adaptations are needed before the improved fixtures are *3D-print*.

It happens that someone comes up with another procedure that goes faster and then the fixture also needs to be redone. It can on another workstation's conditions, where the screwdriver and other tools are placed. The main purpose is that it should both feel good and go quite fast. This also depends on the skills of the operator as well as the material in that particular product.

“It's usually that we want to get a feel for it first. I mean, you need to know the feeling assembling all components. So, when it has gone from the prototype stage to the assembly, then we have to try to either put our heads together right away or try to see if there is a reasonable procedure. Like, "I noticed this when I was assembling" or "should we do like this instead" and, then you can anticipate a bit like this.” [The assembler, pointing to one of the fixtures on the table.]

Figure 1: On the left of the image, the hard plastic fixture is mainly 3D printed, but supplemented with metal pins because the assembler's part showed that the fixture's function as a 'third hand' did not work for the lock component on the right of the image.

Method developers routinely walk around and watch how assemblers work and discuss changes to the procedure when they think it looks particularly complicated.

“I think that, as long as we use fixtures, anyone can do it their way and you do it another way, and the other way is not wrong, as long as we get the same result in the end. Then, the fixture becomes controlling, because you can only put the components together in a certain way.” (Method developer)

Fixture – “the third hand”

The work of assembling mechanical locks develops a high degree of craftsmanship. As workers within the work team are encouraged to rotate between different workstations and types of locks, competence has traditionally been conveyed via the fixture. The practical function beyond being the assembler's "third hand" can thus have the important

but unreflected function to capture and maintain the work teams' collective practice and creativity in the development processes and problem solving.

Figure 2: A workstation for assembly of marine locks. On the left in the centre of the image are the components that are put together using the fixture which is the black perforated 3D printed plastic piece on the right in the centre of the image.

The fixtures consist of different materials, for example wood or so-called MDF. It is much simpler, quick to saw and quick to adjust. No one expected that fixture to work and last very long.

“Yes, it's probably possible to actually assemble the components from just looking at the fixture. But then there are other aspects like, how hard should you pull for example, that kind of information or instruction is not in the fixture itself.” (Assembler)

Yes, there are a lot of thinking and iteration, in the assembly work team about work procedures. And this is taken into considerations in the fixture design, and this have consequences for the way we work, both ergonomically and in terms of time and so on. (Method developer)

In the use of this 3D printed fixture (figure 1), certain hand grips and actions are made possible while alternative ditto is made impossible. This paradoxical function of the work team's collective creative agency is particularly interesting given that the interlocking components are fixed together.

Training and learning in practice.

Fixtures also become a pedagogical tool when beginners are trained in how to assemble a specific lock. It is often the method developer who provide the initial instructions, but the acquisition of the craftsmanship is based on trial-and-error, making mistakes, and solving problems that arise on one's own. The method developer reasons based on a problem situation that recently arose during the training period of an apprentice.

“So, for example, when I said to the apprentice, “You have to screw these components together like this, do you understand?” then she answers “Yes!” But then it turns out that it doesn't work, so she doesn't understand that she doesn't understand... and I don't mean that she's stupid, of course!” (Method developer)

During the reasoning about the lack of commitment and willingness to adopt new instructions and solve problems on their own, the assembler connects to the infected discussion in the work team that they are expected to rotate between the workstations and business areas as the business model “low volume and high mix” implies.

Commitment to the business can be expressed in different ways, such as being flexible, understanding new instructions and solving problems. The method developer reflects on how the attitude and understanding of craftsmanship really entails has changed over time.

“Maybe we hired people who didn't understand, but I think it's also about interest and caring about the whole process. I think people used to be more curious and that's how you really learn things, the hard way. Nowadays, educated people come with higher salaries, but they still have to learn the hard way. But now, they just go on like that [without checking], don't seem to have any problems with the manager or anyone scolding them. But when I grew up and started working, I really wanted to avoid scolding as much as possible. You don't want to be seen as a machine.” (Method developer)

Creativity – flexibility, problem solving, tinkering, and fixing.

The method developer believes that creativity is about making something work and that this is exactly what he spends a large part of his working day on. It started already this morning, with me getting a new device working. Creativity also means being careful not to settle for something that works, but also to improve the quality and at the same time simplify, not complicate things unnecessarily.

“It's important to check if there are any flaws in the components and to fix them directly, even if they say we shouldn't. You see, if something doesn't quite work, it's only half finished. Then I think we could solve it in-house, but nowadays that's not the right thing to do.” (Assembler)

Yeah, like filing the components, for example. You know, the CEO and his gang started saying: "You shouldn't have to file, you damn well shouldn't!" On the one hand, I can agree with that, but when you are in the assembly process, then you have to. "Ah, there is something wrong with this component, but we have to get it out to the customer. Well, I'll do some filing and I'll put it all together. So, you go back into the process to fix it, great, but then the next time it might be the same problem. It's all about time! We don't sit down around here and wait for a job to come or a new component to arrive - we solve the problem so that we can continue. (Method developer)

Case 2: AR-technology pilot test

Context and preparation

The programmer set-up the equipment (computer and software running, headset with glasses) and the material (a printed A3 function as structuring the lock-components, i.e., instead of a fixture, and all the physical components and tools needed for the assembly of the physical lock. All those physical components have also been transformed into 3D-objects archived in the AR-software. The AR-software also control instructional videos including short sequences of handgrips and the components placements in the lock house.

The apprentice sits down at the table. He begins to put the headset including the 3D-glasses on his head and adjust everything. It is especially tricky because he uses ordinary glasses as well. The programmer, which is also acting as a technical coach, give comments and instructs the apprentice on how to proceed. The programmer simultaneous informs the participative observers what will happen during the testing procedure.

Relating physical and digital objects

The program shows arrows pointing to the levers in the fixture that the apprentice will install next. He looks back and forth at them and expresses frustration that it is very difficult to see through the 3D glasses which physical levers he should pick up from the fixture on the table in front of him.

“Yes, exactly, in the workstation where these locks are assembled, there is a drawer for each lever, and all the drawers are numbered from one to seven from left to right, and it's super clear.” (Expert)

The programmer just nods his head a little, not confirming that he understands what the expert is talking about. That is, that the design of the fixture is extremely important. The programmer to the apprentice: *It doesn't matter if you make a mistake now... if it goes wrong, it's the fault of the instructions.*

Supporting collective practices

The programmer provides detailed instructions for the apprentice to understand and perform each step. Those participants observing the testing procedure are able to see the computer screen, but they do not see exactly the same view as the apprentice, wearing glasses, when the instructor or mainly the apprentice for example are pointing straight out into the thin air to grab a 3D object, in the physical world these actions looks like he is groping for something invisible.

The expert's comment that it is the programmers doing the assembly is not innocent or intended as a joke. In previous interviews, he has pointed out several times how important it is that it is a skilled craftsman who shows how the work procedures should be carried out in order for it to be correct from the beginning and to avoid costly adjustments afterwards and in the worst case that incorrect locks are sent out to the customer who then advertises the product, etc.

Evaluating discussion after pilot testing of AR-application.

It is striking how the ones promoting the technology tout the potential benefits and strengths of the technology (the vision they have), despite the fact that the actual application just presented and used is very flawed and actually does not even meet the basic features in specifications.

Pedagogical aspects

“We should instead think of the this as a teacher, like a guide, it should teach new people.” (Site manager)

“It would certainly be very useful for any kind of remote assist, it's like a journey, going somewhere but not knowing exactly how/what to do. In remote assistance, for example, there is no instruction, but then it is based on the competence of the user.” (CEO)

“Here we know what problems can occur and then we have an instruction for it... and then we have control over it.” (Programmer)

Time consuming preparations

“In the three sessions we have had here, we have captured the process and the assembly itself. Then we have sat down to put these different parts together, we know roughly how many there are, that are important. Then when it comes to creating this design, I would say it takes just as much time. And then when it comes to working in the tool (HoloLens) itself and creating instructions, it's pretty quick. What takes the most time is to capture what needs to be instructed, that is, 1) what needs to be said and shown, 2) how to do it in a good way, how should we cut videos, long enough or short enough, 3) then some text should be inserted, 4) then comes this with the videos, but we didn't have time for that now, it's about audio recording of someone reading the instructions, and if we should do that, then it becomes even more, depending on the level.” (Programmer)

The compilation of comprehensive planning meetings, i.e., not the actual development/programming in the AR environment, is in total about 16 hours.

Summary of contrasting findings

The contrasting analysis is summarized in the table. This study was expected to shed light on whether the tested AR technology's assembly instructions can expand, replace, or at least not inhibit the work team's cultivated creative agency.

Table 1: The main themes from the contrasting analysis of the findings from case 1 and case 2.

<i>Comparable aspects.</i>	<i>Case 1: Fixture methodology</i>	<i>Case 2: AR-technology test</i>	<i>Advantages and disadvantages.</i>
Skill development	The method and prototype developer are testing alternative approaches for how all components can be assembled into a fully functional lock.	The programmer needs to familiarize himself with the technical inner workings of the lock. How the components look and work together to open or lock.	Resources, time and competence
Sharing and exchange	The lock installed in the best (most efficient) way is shown to the customer who provides feedback and confirms correct operation.	The programmer needs to observe how an experienced lock assembly expert actually behaves, which hand grips and the order in which the components are placed next to each other.	Craft skills potentiality: Augmentation, disruption versus creative combinations of differences.
Affordances and materiality	One or more design proposals for fixtures to facilitate the assembly procedure are tested by one or two lock operators.	Tampered perception in augmented reality: 3D-objects increasing mental fixation.	The effect of mental fixation versus instances for skill development.

The results of the contrasting analysis are discussed in the following chapter.

5 Results and discussion

In this study of an industrial design firms mixed eco-system, we have examined the relationships between joint learning, collaborative creativity, physical assembly fixtures and fixation via digital AR-based instructions. This exploration revealed much about the benefits and limits of both approaches, but also about the ways in which skilled workers learn and retain knowledge.

In artisanal manufacturing processes, the relationship between the parts and the whole is important to understand, on several levels. Familiarity with the nature of the material that the components are made of is important, often the operators need to make material choices for each new work order. The reasons behind a particular component's design and manufacturing procedure are not readily apparent from the drawing or instructions (if any). This reason for a certain design appears much later in the assembly of the components where, for example, a small recess in one component is required for another component to work together with other moving components in, for example, a lever tumbler lock.

Yet another understanding aspect of the relationship between the components and the whole is actualized when all components are correctly positioned in relation to each other in the lock's case and are to be screwed together. Finally, the operator needs to understand and determine which components need to be sufficiently greased and at the same time which components must absolutely not come into contact with the grease inside the lock box as it will quickly render the lock unusable.

The quality of, for example, a lock for a high-security institution is not necessarily the same as ensuring that all components have exact measured dimensions according to the specifications of the drawings. That is, the quality is not guaranteed by the precision during the production of the components, but that the lock as a whole works with high reliability. That the components are correct is a basic requirement, but quality check is based on the integrated functions of the components.

The company has an established practice for developing and using fixtures, including collaborative iteration between prototyping and testing. Though these fixtures are not conceived of as stores of collective knowledge *about* assembly (this is our interpretation of them) despite having the function of augmenting existing instructions, such as drawings, capturing and mediating work procedures and supporting the development and sharing of skills among workers. In addition, this iterative collective practice constituted unreflected creative processes that nevertheless supported the development, maintaining and sharing this community of practice.

Faraj and Azad (in Leonardi et al. 2012) discuss how objects relational affordances can capture handgrips and maintain skills. Repeated use of a fixture by different operators, collective understanding, skills, and handgrips are established, allowing some, excluding others. During the development of fixtures, activities are included that raise awareness of which handgrips are included in the assembly procedure of a specific lock. In the iterative exchange of prototypes between the operator and the developer, conditions such as ergonomic requirements and the location of the tools, quality and time aspects are included. Primary is the flow of the work procedure, that the fixture allows smooth procedure and at the same time conveys how the components of a specific lock should be joined together. This was discussed in the dialogue interview with the method developer and fixture user (assembler) regarding competences and practice captured in physical object such as fixtures appears (Corazza & Glaveanu, 2020).

Aim of testing AI/AR-technology.

The management's intention to increase the competence, flexibility, and motivation of the workers by investing in the potential that augmented reality technology might bring contrasts with the collective creative community of practice of the work team.

The aim of testing this particular AI/AR-technology is also based on the company experiencing difficulties of attracting and hiring competent staff. Implementing digitalized tools and gamification-oriented interfaces for all kinds of work tasks including introductory training utilizing augmented reality becomes a strategy for increasing the workplace attractivity.

However previous research has found that objects in an augmented reality can have the effect of increasing mental fixation, hindering divergent phases of creative processes and thus flexibility which is a highly valued capability for realizing the company's business model "high mix and low volume". These digital 3D-objects should be compared with the ordinary (traditional) use of fixtures in the assembly procedures within the company, they rather constitute a physical instance for the work team's collective creativity, where problem solving, and craft practice are made visible and become shareable.

The fixture contrasted with the AR solution in that its development was *limited* to within the firm - allowing for *closer* interactions and denser *iterative* knowledge exchange. This felt natural and organic – a joint learning activity involving feed-back loops, teaching others and the *embodying* of all of this in a physical artefact, the fixture – even if it was used differently by different parties. This contrasted with the iterative development of the VR, which involved an additional technology, new types of work programming (done externally) and additional (external) human actors who clearly did not have prior access to the collective knowledge that circulated within the firm. The need for the programmer to go away and re-code certain aspects made for a slow and cumbersome learning process – one in which, we should note, the programmer was entangled or personally invested as a member of that learning community of practice. This *transgressing* of the organisational boundary, that brought in 'outside' actors, organisations and techniques, ones that had not grown organically within the firm, creating a jarring experience, it seemed, for those involved – disrupting learning and knowledge flows by externalising them.

In other words, digital technology, as it is today, is not usually part of the firm's organic *learning relations*. It always brings in extended linkages, actors and objects that fracture the organic development of the firm. The digital is disruptive, but potentially in a destructive way. If the development process unreasonably long, inflexible, and costly, it will be problematic for the business in the longer term if the apprentices are presented with incorrect handling and procedures or inadequate instructions and explanations. With these aspects as background, it is striking how dominant the programmer's understanding of the details of the work processes is. Misunderstandings at this level can mean that routines learned skillfully over many years are completely ignored or turned into costly detours and extended work processes. For example, what the expert points out about the principle of the measuring tool, i.e. that depending on the number and order of the retainers, which can be different in different locks, meaning that certain measuring points in the tool need to be skipped. The problem is that this completely escapes the programmer not showing awareness that what the expert is saying to the apprentice should be important in the improvement of the AR-application. Instead of embracing causal explanations as to why the apprentice has problems with the AR application's instructions, he tells him to be quiet.

Contribution

The analysis of collected data, contrasting findings combining the two cases and subsequent discussion of presented findings have provide increased understanding of what effects AI/A-ethnology based application can entail for craft skills development and the work team's creative agency. Here the overarching question is addressed: *What is augmented, diminished, or disrupted?*

Creativity in a collective, such as a work team, means that the interactants are jointly able to maintain several differences in working methods/techniques, tools, and machines/technologies, while the individuals share their experiences from the respective work procedures with each other on a daily basis. This collective creativity is sedimented into a set of physical fixtures which are then used to assist and guide the assembly of components until a certain specific type of lock has been established in the collective's work procedures. The collective can exercise and maintain their creativity and problem-solving skills by developing and refining their fixtures – they are easy and quick to adapt.

The digital, in this case is slow – characterized not by iteration and joint learning but a long developmental loop requiring the programmer to 'go away', re-think and do more programming – potentially with only limited understanding of the problem.

Consequences necessary iterations of the AR happens slowly – if at all.

Based on this finding we suggest that a new employee/beginner/apprentice should start by getting to know the fixtures, components and observe the work procedures of the assemblers in order to acquire an understanding of what it means to assemble the components into a lock. At a later stage, augmented reality could potentially function as re-fresher for other types of assembly procedures. However, the length of time required to set up and train the AR mean that it is not suitable for the short assembly runs.

This study highlights the importance of creativity in collaboration and development processes, it shows that creative abilities are needed to deal with challenges that arise in a work environment. With creative approaches and processes, the integration of different perspectives and beliefs can be combined, temporarily unite divergent perspectives and understandings in convergent agreements.

Practical implications

The contribution to the innovation management community that this exploratory study makes is primarily increased understanding of the relationship between collective (and individual) creative agency and the impact of AR-based work instructions on this.

The role of crafts in organizational eco-social transformation and digitalization is crucial in workplace practices, that includes empowerment of craftspeople, collective creativity, and relational skill development.

It is important that the work team understands the way the work is organized as a consequence of the fact that the business, its business model, is characterized by "low volume, high mix" - which in turn means a high degree of flexibility in the work.

Regarding the pedagogical aspects the developers: programmer and designer, should follow the company's ordinary training mentoring program for apprentices. What and how the mentor is doing and showing in comparison with verbal instructions would be very beneficial to consider in the development of this kind of substituting AR-application. Regarding the time needed to develop this kind of AR-application, it falls into its own absurdity that anyone could ever "go straight to it" and perform such a complex task with any kind of usability/functionality/quality intention.

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